

Classroom Interaction Patterns and Students' Learning Outcomes in Biology in Calabar South Secondary Schools, Cross River State.

Osomasi, Richard Aja

Department of Curriculum and Instructional Technology

Faculty of Education, University of Cross River State, Calabar, Nigeria

richardosomasi518@gmail.com

+234806 847 3220

Abstract

This research investigates the influence of classroom interaction patterns and students' learning outcomes in biology in Calabar South Secondary Schools, Cross River State. To achieve this, three research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated to direct the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The population comprised of two thousand two hundred and twenty-eight (2,228) senior secondary two biology students from ten (10) public secondary schools. Five schools were sampled using simple random sampling techniques with proportionate allocation. In the five schools, the SSII Biology students numbering two hundred and sixty-four (264) were selected using the Taro Yamane Formula to determine the minimum sample size for the study. Two instruments were used in the study, namely Classroom Interaction Patterns (CIP) and Biology Achievement Test (BAT), designed by the researcher and validated by experts in Test and Measurement as well as one Biology expert. The data collected were analysed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). From the analysis of the data collected for the study and test of hypotheses, the result revealed that there is a significant relationship between social interaction patterns and biology students learning outcomes in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area; and that there is a significant relationship between teacher-student interaction patterns and biology students learning outcomes in secondary schools in Calabar South LGA. It was also observed that there is a significant relationship between student-student learning outcomes in secondary schools in Calabar South LGA. The study recommends, among others, that the government should make the platform for social interaction among biology teachers and students to be effective, thereby enhancing healthy learning outcomes, especially in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

1. Introduction

The interaction between teachers and students is an essential part of students' involvement in the classroom. Classroom interaction patterns stimulate students' learning outcomes in biology as they fuel students' motivation. Turnburg (2005) defined classroom interaction patterns as the learner's engagement with the course content, other learners, and the technological medium used in the course.

Effective teaching and learning demand more of the student's interaction pattern than just listening to the instruction. Hence, effective classroom interaction is very essential in today's act of teaching and learning. Classroom interaction is the relationship that exists between the teacher and students in the classroom in the course of teaching and learning (Igbokwe, 2005). It is a practice that enhances the development of the two very important language skills, which are speaking and listening, among the learners. Classroom interaction helps the learners to be competent enough to think critically and share their views among their peers (Ghosh, 2010).

Through classroom interaction patterns, the learners will be able to get themselves involved with concepts, ideas, and various other devices and products for language and culture learning. Good interaction patterns in the classroom also help the students to identify their own learning methods, guide them to communicate with their peers easily, give them exposure to learning, and enhance their academic outcomes in their subject. For Sita (2010), classroom interaction patterns are everyday activities between the teacher and the learners. Interaction is commonly defined as a kind of action that occurs when two or more objects have an effect on one another. The idea of a two-way effect is essential in the concept of interaction, as opposed to a one-way casual effect. Education, with its correlated activities of teaching and learning processes, involves interaction between teacher and students as channels for realising its objectives. Teachers have access to many methods of creating an interactive classroom. Common methods include classroom discussion, questions, answers, reading out loud, role playing, etc. Damon (2016) sees other forms of classroom interaction patterns as ways for students to learn and understand how to work with partners. Questions and answers are a common classroom interaction with the students. The teacher may ask the students in relation to the earlier interaction he/she had passed across to them. Reading loudly is also common among primary and secondary school students, as the teacher may ask the students to recite after him/her or assign the students to read some portion of a textbook to the hearing of every member of the class.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Elevis Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Osomasi, Richard Aja

According to Siddiqui (2005), interaction between teacher and students is an essential part of teaching and learning process. It promotes involvement, enhances learning, and increases motivation. It promotes a shift from a teacher-centred to a student-centred environment while maintaining a teacher-led activity. There has been a paradigm shift in modern times to promote classroom instructiveness. In this context, a learning strategy that promotes interaction between the instructor and the learner as well as among learners is sought, and it is seen as pivotal to improving pupils' communicative skills in the classroom and, at length, impacting their learning outcomes. Koli (2010) adds that classroom interactions are one of the basic facilitators of students' academic performance, and in an effort to bring home the benefits of classroom interaction, Oyinloye (2008) argues that if teachers provide learners with enough interactive opportunities, then students learning outcomes are bound to be magnified.

Classroom discussion is a situation wherein students within a particular class interact between themselves on issues about what they have been taught. It offers students the opportunity to test ideas and opinions against the ideas and opinions of their peers. Therefore, it is important to consider the relationship between classroom interaction patterns and students learning outcomes. The students learning outcomes can be mature in terms of their grades in both internal and external examinations, presentations, and interactive skills.

Hence, the study will focus on examining the classroom interaction patterns and students' learning outcomes in biology in Calabar South Secondary Schools, Cross River State.

Statement of the Problem

It is no longer news to hear that the quality of education in Nigeria and Calabar, specifically, is diminishing. Many social commentators had attributed the situation to the inability of the federal, state, and local governments to finance or fund the educational sector. Others have blamed it on the quality and qualifications of teachers in schools. Much has been said about the declining classroom interaction patterns, especially with the advent and proliferation of mobile phones, which have deviated the attention and focus of many, including teachers and students.

The reading and communication skills of students are also declining as students now speak and write in *shorthand*, which makes them speak English that is not

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Osomasi, Richard Aja

comprehensible. It is a common trend in our societies. It is also seen that teachers and students no longer show interest in questions and answers, reading aloud, or classroom discussion. One will wonder whether all of the above-mentioned factors have a significant impact on students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to critically examine the classroom interaction patterns and students' learning outcomes in biology in Calabar South Secondary Schools, Cross River State.

The study seeks specifically to;

1. To ascertain the impact of social interaction patterns on biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area.
2. To examine the influence of teacher-student interaction patterns on biology students' learning outcomes in Secondary School in Calabar South Local Government Area.
3. To ascertain the influence of student-student interaction patterns on biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area

Research Questions

1. To what extent does classroom social interaction pattern influence biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area.
2. How does teacher-students interaction pattern influence biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area.
3. To what extent does student-students interaction pattern impact biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship between social interaction patterns and biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleliv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Osomasi, Richard Aja

Hypothesis two: There is no significant relationship between students' interaction patterns and biology learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant relationship between student-students interaction pattern and biology students learning outcome in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area

2. Methodology

The research design adopted for the study was a survey research design. The survey research design is more relevant to be used for this study because it enables the researcher to gather firsthand information from the respondents on the subject matter. The area of the study is the Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The population of this study consists of 2,228 senior secondary II (SSII) biology students in ten public secondary schools in the Calabar South Local Government Area. A simple random sampling technique was used for the study. The Taro Yamane Formula was used to select two hundred and sixty-four (264) students as the minimum sample size for the study. The sample of this study consisted of 264 senior secondary two (SSII) biology students drawn from five (5) public secondary schools in the area, both male and female. This selection ensured an adequate representation of males and females in the sample. The sample was approximately 10.94% of the total population of students from public secondary schools in the study area. The data for this study was collected with the aid of questionnaires that were administered to each school. The collected data were analysed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.5 level of significance.

3. Data Analysis and Interpretation of Result

Hypothesis one

This hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between social interaction pattern and biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South Local Government Area. To test this hypothesis, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistical Analysis was used. The result of the analysis is presented in table 2 below:

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Osomasi, Richard Aja

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between social interaction patterns and Biology students' learning outcomes. N = 264

Variable	\sum_x	\sum_x^2	\sum_{xy}	r-cal
	\sum_y	\sum_y^2		
Social interaction pattern	1780	23610		
			143210	0.62
Learning outcome in Biology	2487	24360		

*Significant at 0.05, df = 263, Critical r = 0.138

The result of the analysis presented in the table 2 shows that there is a significant relationship between social interaction patterns and biology students' outcomes in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State with $r\text{-cal} = 0.627$, $r\text{-critical} = 0.138$, respectively.

Hence, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected at 0.5 level of significance with 262 degree of freedom.

Hypothesis Two

This hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between teacher-student interaction patterns and biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South LGA. To test this hypothesis, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistical Analysis was used. The result is presented in the Table 3.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between teacher-student interaction pattern in Biology students learning outcome in secondary school in Calabar South LGA. N = 264

Variable	\sum_x	\sum_x^2	\sum_{xy}	r-cal
	\sum_y	\sum_y^2		
Teacher – student Interaction Pattern	2516	52068		
			52343	0.79
Learning outcome in Biology	2394	46485		

*Significant at 0.05, df = 262, Critical r = 0.138

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Elevis Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Osomasi, Richard Aja

The result of the analysis presented in the table above shows that there is a significant relationship between teacher-student interaction patterns in biology students' learning outcomes in secondary schools in Calabar South LGA, Cross River State. ($r\text{-cal} = 0.797$, $r\text{-critical} = 0.138$).

Hence, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected at 0.05 level of significance with 262 degree of freedom.

Hypothesis Three

This hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between student-student interaction patterns and biology students' learning outcomes in secondary schools in Calabar South LGA.

To test this hypothesis, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used. The result of the analysis is presented in table 4 below:

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between student-student interaction patterns and Biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South LGA. N = 264

Variable	\sum_x	\sum_x^2	\sum_{xy}	r-cal
	\sum_y	\sum_y^2		
Student-students Interaction Pattern	2525	83106	43320	0.68
Learning outcome in Biology	2284	36405		

*Significant at 0.05, df = 262, Critical r = 0.138

The result of the analysis presented in the table above shows that there is a significant relationship between student-student interaction patterns and biology students' learning outcomes in secondary school in Calabar South LGA, Cross River State. ($r\text{-cal} = 0.687$, $r\text{-critical} = 0.138$)

Hence, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected at 0.05 level of significance with 262 degree of freedom.

4. Discussion of Findings

This section discusses the findings obtained from the study based on the hypotheses formulated to guide the study.

Social Interaction Patterns and Biology Students' Learning Outcomes

The findings from the first hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between social interaction patterns and biology students learning outcomes. The findings are in line with the work of Isaac (2013), who posited that a social interaction pattern promotes the development of study habits among students. The students' social interaction patterns would enable them to acquire new skills, knowledge, and ideas, which could foster a good learning outcome in biology.

Teacher-student Interaction patterns and Biology Students' Learning Outcomes

The findings of this hypothesis revealed that teacher-student interaction patterns have a significant relationship with secondary school biology students' learning outcomes. The findings are in line with the work of Tairab (2014), who opined that teacher-student interaction has helped biology students' learning outcomes in practical work done in the laboratory.

Student-Student Interaction Patterns and Biology Students' Learning Outcomes

This theme addresses how well students communicate with one another in class. Classes where students have opportunities to communicate with each other help students effectively construct their knowledge by emphasising the collaborative and cooperative nature of scientific work. Students share responsibility for learning with each other, discuss divergent understandings, and shape the direction of the class. The pedagogy in action module on cooperative learning is a great place to learn more about structuring student-student interaction both in and out of the classroom. The cutting-edge teaching method module on using concepts in the classroom also has tips for integrated think-pair-share activities into even large classrooms.

5. Conclusion

From the analysis of the data and the test of hypotheses, it is concluded that social interaction patterns, teacher-student interaction patterns, and student-student interactions have a significant positive influence on their learning outcomes in biology.

6. Recommendations

1. Government should make the platform for social interaction patterns among students to be effective, thereby enhancing healthy and south learning outcomes in biology.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Osomasi, Richard Aja

2. The quality of teacher-student interaction patterns should be advanced and made highly effective to encourage teaching and learning which would in turn enhance learning outcomes.
3. There should be an in-house debate among students as this will enable the peers to interact freely with one another.

References

- Akuma, N. (2005) Effects of guided discovery method on senior secondary school student's achievement in map work. *The journal of world council of curriculum and instruction of Nigeria. Chapter 5(2), 185-194.*
- Aniekwe, (2002) Effects of student's interaction pattern on cognitive retention and interest in chemistry doctorate dissertation department of science education. University of Nigeria Nsukka.
- Aormby, A.S. (2001). Oxford advance learner's dictionary of English (6th ed) Oxford University press.
- Awal, H. (2010) classroom interaction in English, mathematics and science classes. Retrieved from; <http://acanpbrarehost.com>
- Cooper, J & Robinson. P. (2000) informal small strategies in large classes in Macgragn, T. J., Cooper, K.T. Smith & Rebinson P. (eds) strategies for emerging for energizing large classes: from small groups of long communities. New direction for teaching and learning.
- Gosh A. (2010). Classroom interaction: part 1 (definition, objective, types, teachers role and merits). Available online: <http://www.examinar.com/article/classroominteraction>
- Igbokwe J. C. (2005). Learner-centered teacher student relationship are effective. A Meta-analysis, review of Educational Research, 78 (2), 53-55

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Osomasi, Richard Aja

- Kalu, I. (2008) Classroom interaction patterns, teachers and student's characteristics and student learning outcome journal of social science 3(i), 57-60
- Koli Calling (2010). 10th Koli Calling international conference on computing education research, Koli calling 10, Koli, Finland, October 28-31.
- Kouicem K. (2012) the effect of classroom interaction on developing the learner speaking skills. *Journal of classroom interaction* 39(2) 1-27.
- Metalo, A. (2006) describing classroom retrieved online file: *llc. Document 20% and 20% setting/administrator my%20 document/contitled: Htm 20th December, 2017.*
- Okoli, J. (2011) activity. Based approach and use of analogy for effective teaching of organization of life using organism. In Okoli J.J. N & Nzewi, U. M. (eds) proceeding of national biology pauel workshop series pp 8-15.
- Okoye, P. O. (2011) influence of instructional resources on the successful implementation of biology of biology curriculum in senior secondary school.
- Oleritan, S. O. and Nwoke, G. I. (2000). Practical researcher methods in education Onitsha: Summer educational publisher Ltd.
- Onimisi, J. A. (2006). Impact of types of teacher training on student's achievement and attitude towards integrated science in Kogi State. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, University of Nyrrii Nsukka.
- Oyinloye, R. O. (2008). A Geo-Information-Based Model for Assessing and Monitoring Forest Reserves in Southwestern Nigeria, Department of Geography, Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU), Nigeria, 337 p
- West African Examination Council (2010-2015) chief report SSCE may/june, Yaba Lagos WAEC.